

Report on the NZ Species edit-a-thons 2025

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Slide 1 of the NZ Species Edit-a-thon slidedeck, by Siobhan Leachman and Heidi Meudt 2025. [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Event details

Organisers: Siobhan Leachman (SL [User:Ambrosia10](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/User:Ambrosia10)), Heidi Meudt (HM [User:Stitchbird2](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/User:Stitchbird2)) and Christine Richardson (CR [User:Noracrentiss](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/User:Noracrentiss)),

Support: Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand funding as well as administrative support

Venue: Ōtari-Wilton's Bush, Wellington, New Zealand

Dates: 2 and 9 August, 2025

Theme: New Zealand species

Aims: Onboarding and upskilling new Wikipedia editors, improving Wikipedia articles about NZ species, adding species images to Wikimedia Commons, and widen the network of the Wiki editing community in Wellington

Organisation

Planning meetings

Introduction

Building on the success of the 2024 Edit-a-thon held in October and November, organisers CR, SL, and HM committed to hosting another series of events in 2025. They reached out to Wellington Gardens to confirm whether they would once again host the event, and to find two dates when the Leonard Cockayne Centre would be available.

Meeting Schedule:

- Planning resumed in April 2025 with fortnightly Zoom meetings.
- Meetings shifted to weekly as the August event approached.
- No meetings were held in June due to one organiser's temporary unavailability.

Documentation and Resource Development:

- A new [Google Doc](#) was created to record meeting notes and track tasks.
- Additional Docs and Sheets supported the creation of resources, including the [introductory slide deck](#).
- A dedicated [Google Drive folder](#) for the 2025 event was established to organise materials separately from the 2024 event.
- Both annual folders are now housed within a master "[Species Wiki Edit-a-thons](#)" folder for streamlined record-keeping and future planning.

Organisation Communication Channels:

- The existing WhatsApp group and email remained key tools for ongoing communication.
- Additional Zoom sessions were held as needed for collaborative resource development and time-sensitive discussions.

Timeline:

- All planning and logistics were completed within a two-month window (May and July), ensuring readiness for the August event.

Venue: Leonard Cockayne Centre

The venue was generally excellent:

- Information on how to access the venue was delivered in a timely manner.
- On both Saturdays, the passwords provided by WCC did not work, so we used WellyWifi which was excellent.
- TV and cables were all provided.
- Trestle tables were extremely heavy but therefore very stable.
- Mobility access was good.

- There was good access to electrical outlets, toilets and kitchen facilities.
- Ōtari's library was (meant to be) made available.
- There was excellent access to plant and animal species outside.

Event Marketing and communications

The organisers created two Wikipedia edit-a-thon event pages, [one for 2 August](#) (which was a “take over” of the usual Wellington meetup) and [one for 9 August](#), and used these links to assist with outreach and event advertising. Two outreach dashboards, one for the [2nd of August](#) and one for the [9th of August](#), were created to track edits during the events. Dianne at WANZ set up [one Humanitix page](#) where people could register for one or both events at \$5 per event.

[User:Quilt Phase](#) created a [Wikimedia Commons category](#) to assist with the organisation of media and images created for and during the edit-a-thon, and in fact took most of the images added to that category. This category also includes a [copy of the google slide deck used for both days](#) which was edited to take out duplicate slides and then uploaded into Wikimedia Commons under that category.

We were very fortunate to have the support of the WANZ Marketing and Communications Coordinator Sophie Sparrow (SS) who helped with developing a [Communications Plan](#) that included methods for targeting different audiences via specific platforms, such as:

- Social media graphics and key messaging copy for posting on various platforms, by both WANZ and event organisers.
- Directly contacting aligned organisations and people to ask them to share the event among their networks, i.e. Zealandia, Wellington Zoo, Science Communication at Victoria University, Predator Free Wellington).
 - Predator Free Wellington promoted the event on their [Facebook](#) and [Instagram](#) accounts.
 - Nicola Toki (Forest & Bird CEO) shared the event on her Instagram – this led to RNZ reaching out and a [resulting interview](#).
- Share the event in several relevant Facebook groups ([Conservation Communicators Aotearoa](#), [Science Communicators Association of New Zealand](#), [Native New Zealand](#), [Predator Free Miramar](#)) and the private NZ Wikipedia group.
- Designed a poster for Wellington Gardens to place in their venues, and some new relevant WANZ swag options for attendees (tūi globe stickers, weevil bookmarks).
- Sending a follow-up email from WANZ to new editors following the event, thanking them for participating and introducing them to the community.

The organisers, with the welcome support of SS, also undertook various communication efforts to advertise the event via email to a variety of potentially interested groups and people. SL also advertised the event to personal social media platforms such as Twitter, Bluesky, Facebook, Mastodon and LinkedIn. The event was advertised on both the Wellington and Aotearoa Wiki meetup pages as well as on the WikiProject New Zealand talk page. The organisers again used their own contacts in the local, regional and national scientific and citizen science communities to spread the word, including writing articles for the NZ Plant Conservation Network [June](#) and [July](#) newsletters, and short news items for the

Glean Report, and the Royal Society Bulletin Alert. The Wellington Gardens team at Wellington City Council also promoted our events on their social media pages, again reusing the short videos ([one by HM](#) and [one by SL](#)) made in 2024 inviting people to our event.

The organisers believed that the communication strategy for these events was definitely improved in comparison to the 2024 events as a result of the advice, writings and actions of SS and would like to thank her for her valuable contributions.

Funding

Our [funding application](#) to Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand was successful. The grant covered the cost of catering across both days of the event, as well as a donation to the Ōtari-Wilton's Bush Trust. We were also generously granted free use of the Leonard Cockayne Centre by Wellington City Council, including access to its Wi-Fi. Although the Centre's wifi was unavailable during the event, we were able to use WellyWifi as an alternative. The provision of the venue at no cost significantly reduced our overall expenses. We opted not to include funds for 'swag' in the grant application as items were available by WANZ.

Day 1: Saturday 2 August 2025

Introduction

People were warmly welcomed to the Leonard Cockayne Centre venue at Ōtari-Wilton's Bush on arrival around 10 am by CR, SL and HM. Tea, coffee and snacks were available on arrival and on a help-yourself basis all day. Although there were 12 paid sign ups, 9 of these attended the event, which meant that including the organisers, we were a total of 12 people participating on Day 1 of the edit-a-thon.

After the karakia, there was a round of self-introductions. This included asking participants to say what their favourite New Zealand species was. The purpose of this was to provide an opportunity not just for the participants to introduce themselves but also to act as an icebreaker and to give organisers an indication of areas of interest for editing.

We learned from last year's event and provided name stickers for attendees which assisted attendees engaging with each other.

A brief [slide deck presentation](#) was given by the organisers to give participants housekeeping information, to introduce the new editors to Wikipedia and to assist them in learning how to edit.

Resources

- SL brought several books from her personal collection which were used by several of the attendees for their editing (on Day 1 and Day 2).

- Ōtari-Wiltons Bush offered to support us by bringing several books from their library for use at the event. However, this was not actually done on either day.

[Editors working together on day 1](#). Tom Ackroyd, [CC BY-SA 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

Content (morning)

It was then time to ensure that the new editors received hands-on training in how to edit Wikipedia. We were fortunate in that there were nearly even numbers of experienced editors to new contributors. This resulted in the new editors being tutored one-on-one.

While SL and HM were assisting new editors without an account to sign up, CR ensured that all participants had been added to the Day 1 Dashboard. Everyone got stuck into improving

the text on a Wikipedia page for a New Zealand species either from the [spreadsheet](#) provided, or of their own choosing, with help from other editors where required.

Lunch break

We took on board a recommendation from Lucy Schrader following the [Te Papa Exhibitions Edit-a-thon](#) in July 2024, and which we also implemented at last year's event, which was to "enforce" a set time for a break for lunch. We were fortunate to have a lovely outdoor space immediately outside the Centre as well as a beautiful sunny day. This meant participants spent time talking to each other which helped create a sense of community and collaboration.

[Lunch break on the sunny afternoon of day 1 of the edit-a-thon](#). Tom Ackroyd, [CC BY-SA 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

Content (afternoon)

Tim Park, manager of Ōtari-Wilton's Bush, joined the meeting after lunch and was ably interviewed by CR. After his interview he talked with HM and SL about Ōtari-Wilton's 100 year anniversary in 2026. He explained the plans for a Bioblitz likely during the City Nature Challenge 2026 event which is to be held from the 24 - 27 April 2026. Tim was keen for there to be a wiki presence at this Bioblitz similar to the [wiki outreach](#) undertaken at the Wellington Botanic Garden Bioblitz in 2019.

The organisers see this as a fabulous opportunity to educate both the general public, the scientists and the citizen scientists involved in the upcoming Bioblitz about editing Wikipedia

as well as the impact this has on iNaturalist, the main platform that is to be used during the Bioblitz. We will be pursuing this idea soon.

After Tim's interview, the edit-a-thon participants were encouraged to continue to edit the Wikipedia pages they had chosen to work on.

[Editors listening to Tim Park speak on day 1](#). Tom Ackroyd, [CC BY-SA 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

Wrap Up

At the conclusion of the day, HM and SL wrapped up with a very short slide session reminding participants of the time, date and location of Day 2 of the edit-a-thon, information on resources supporting editing, providing email addresses to enable participants to reach out for support. Time was then given to attendees to fill in the event survey, with an aim of planning topics and themes (and making improvements) for Day 2 of the edit-a-thon. The organisers also showed the preliminary dashboard results of our collective Day 1 efforts, and asked attendees to volunteer to talk about anything they learned, found useful, or really enjoyed. Everyone including the organisers shared a story, which again promoted community building and collaboration.

Finally the organisers encouraged participants to become a member of [Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand \(WANZ\)](#). A karakia was said to close the day.

In the evening, after the event finished, SL ensured all new editors on the Dashboard had a welcome added onto their talk page. SL followed the feedback given after the 2024 events and used the [Welcome-NZ](#) template.

Feedback Summary:

We received [survey responses from 4 of the 9 attendees](#) summarised below

- Consistent with the 2024 event, feedback was overwhelmingly positive
- All respondents indicated they were either *very satisfied* or *satisfied* with all aspects of the event.
- Participants also noted that Wikipedia editing felt *applicable* or *very applicable* to their personal interests or goals.

New and experienced editors alike mentioned the following skills they learned, such as the very specific “How to cite a source in BHL” to the broader picture:

“The power of Wikipedia to share science information to a wider community. As a marine fisheries scientist, I can see this as a powerful platform to share important science outcomes to a larger audience in a clear and concise manner.”

“I realise that I can edit articles where I don't really know anything, because I know how to find information and turn it into something readable.”

The attendees also appreciated the social aspects of the event, saying that the event was “fantastic”, “inspiring”, and “Really enjoyable and informative. The catering food was amazing.” Other comments:

“I observed passion!”

“So nice to see the knowledge sharing and passion from different people”

How did they hear about the event

The Day 1 editors heard about the event via Facebook or the WANZ newsletter, but two people couldn't remember exactly where they had seen it (a website and/or social media). Finally, 4 of 4 attendees said they were likely or highly likely to edit Wikipedia, join a local Wikimedia community, or attend other Wiki events in future, suggesting that there is enthusiasm and that they may become active editors.

Would you like to attend more Wikipedia edit-a-thons, workshops, meet-ups or conferences?

4 responses

Visualisation generated from the Google survey created by the organisers. [CC BY 4.0](#)

Day 2: Saturday 9 August 2025

Introduction

There were 15 paid sign-ups for Day 2, of whom 12 actually attended (one person had a sick child, another sent their apologies, and one came after lunch), such that there were a total of 15 people participating on Day 2 of the edit-a-thon (including the three organisers). The organisers were extremely gratified to see the high number of repeat attendees (6) from Day 1.

The attendees were again warmly welcomed to the Leonard Cockayne Centre venue at Ōtari-Wilton's Bush. And once again, tea, coffee and biscuits were available both on arrival and on a help-yourself basis all day, contributing to a relaxed and hospitable atmosphere.

Content (morning)

After welcoming all participants, organisers gave housekeeping information and an introduction session where participants introduced themselves. The ice-breaker used this time was "Describe your favourite place to observe biodiversity in New Zealand", which brought out some engaging responses and allowed participants to get to know one another a little better. Experienced editors were then invited to start editing while the repeat of the Day 1 [slide deck](#) was presented to the new editors.

The organisers then requested the new editors to pair off with experienced editors to get an account (where required) and start editing, while the rest of the [slide deck](#) was presented to repeat attendees.

These slides addressed questions raised during Day 1 as well as topics raised when attendees answered the formal feedback survey (e.g. Question: What topics, content, wiki tools or wiki platforms would you like covered (or reviewed) on Day 2...). Some of the topics covered included tools that could be used to upload research-grade openly licensed iNaturalist images into Wikicommons, how to create a new Wikipedia page for a taxon, templates, and installing the View it! tool. After this presentation the repeat attendees also began editing again.

The organisers viewed this method of giving two separate presentations as a satisfactory way to ensure the new attendees were introduced to editing as soon as possible, while at the same time ensuring repeat attendees were upskilled in additional tools and trained to resolve questions or issues they had raised during informal and formal feedback.

[Editors conferring with one another on day 2](#). Tom Ackroyd, [CC BY-SA 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

Lunch

Once again the organisers “enforced” a set time for a break for lunch. The organisers believed this break definitely helped with productivity and also encouraged the collegial atmosphere of the edit-a-thon. Although we were unable to go outside this time due to the weather, editors still took the time to talk to one another during the lunch break.

New Zealand Species Edit-a-thon 2025 group photo from Day 2. Tom Ackroyd, [CC0](#), via Wikimedia Commons.

Content (afternoon)

After lunch, editors continued to edit various Wikipedia pages with experienced editors answering questions and guiding editing. The organisers were gratified to see the rapid advancement of skills in new editors, especially those new editors who were repeat participants.

Wrap up

Prior to the close of the day, HM and SL shared some final wrap-up slides and addressed the issue of what editors should do if they have questions after the edit-a-thon. In the penultimate slide the organisers gave attendees guidance on getting further involved in the Wikimedia movement including how to join WANZ and how to attend in-person and virtual meetups. Finally, attendees were asked to volunteer any stories or learning they wanted to share, and were given a link to the survey for Day 2 and asked to complete it before they left for home.

A karakia was then said and Day 2 of the edit-a-thon was complete.

General comments

We received [survey responses from 5 of the 12 attendees](#) who were not organisers. Feedback and comments were again very positive with attendees being very satisfied with the event, and one commenting, "Thanks so much! I know how much work it is to run these

and you did an awesome job.”

Do you feel you built upon your Wiki knowledge and skills by attending today's workshop?

5 responses

Visualisation generated from the Google survey created by the organisers. [CC BY 4.0](#)

On Day 2, attendees told us they learned additional technical skills such as:

“Lots of wee things actually! It was all useful. Bits and pieces about infoboxes, conventions, I found the Plant Page Template which was very useful!”

“iNaturalist and Commons upload tool forge”

“The visual editor lets me do more of the fiddly stuff than I realised!”

The fact that we had an excellent ratio of new editors to experienced editors meant that one-on-one tutoring was possible and much appreciated:

“As a rank beginner I had more than enough content to keep my mind exercised and very pleasant company in which to do so”

“I really enjoy the in-person collaboration, especially when I can get really focused in on something with an excited new editor.”

“It made a big difference to me to go through an edit with an experienced person and have her available with other edits.”

[Experienced editors working one-on-one with new editors on day 1](#). Tom Ackroyd, [CC BY-SA 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

The attendees, similar to those from 2024, again liked the format of the event over two Saturdays, as it provided flexibility for those who could not attend both days. At the same time, those who could attend both days did not have to give up an entire weekend to do so. Again, the community aspect was highlighted in the comments, e.g.

“Great to see people working together in concentration”

“Heaps of fun, lovely people, thank you!”

How did you find out about the edit-a-thon? Tick all that apply.

5 responses

Visualisation generated from the Google survey created by the organisers. [CC BY 4.0](#).

Finally, we asked how they found out about the event, which may be helpful information for future events (although again the sample size is quite small). The responses included being referred by a friend/colleague (x2), the WANZ newsletter, a Glean Report email, the Wiki Wellington event page, and having been part of an edit-a-thon previously.

Impact

Metrics

Two dashboards were created, one for [Day 1](#) and one for [Day 2](#), to track the contributions of editors. Over 27,000 words were added to Wikipedia, 18 new articles were created (some by the attendees themselves on Day 2), 145 articles were edited, and 295 references were added. These numbers were similar to those from the 2024 event. Once again the aim of improving 100 Wikipedia articles (as stated in the funding application to WANZ) was well exceeded, and in fact it was the exact number improved on Day 2 alone! The Day 2 numbers were higher than the Day 1 numbers, which was likely due to multiple factors, including more editors attending (15 vs 12), and also several editors who were new or attended Day 1 now had the skills, experience and momentum to jump right in on Day 2.

Post-Event Activity

- Emails of organisers HM and SL were given out during the edit-a-thons and multiple offers were made to assist after the event.
- The “NZ welcome” template was added to new editor talk pages.
- All attendees were “thanked” on wiki for at least two or three of their edits by the organisers.
- Participants were emailed the day after both events giving support and links to resources.

- Tim Park was thanked for his participation.
- The [slide presentation was added to Wikimedia Commons](#) in pdf format and placed on both event pages.
- A donation of \$250 was made to Ōtari-Wilton's Bush Trust per our WANZ grant proposal and budget.

The organisers have reported back to the wider wiki communities on these edit-a-thons, i.e, [the GLAMwiki newsletter](#), and have reported back to the Wellington and Aotearoa New Zealand August wiki meetups. SS will write up an article for the next WANZ newsletter.

Recommendations

Prior to the event

- We took on last year's recommendations of using the WANZ Humanitix account for ticketing, working with the WANZ Comms Advisor (who helped provide consistent messaging) and using WANZ swag. We do not have further recommendations from this year's events.

At the event

Virtual Check-ins

- **Recommend** that one person be assigned specific responsibility for managing the "virtual check-ins" aspect of the event. To ensure continuity and effectiveness, this individual should not be involved in one-on-one tutoring. This will allow them to:
 - Keep track of time and conduct the regular check-ins
 - Avoid interrupting learner editors mid-task
 - Maintain access to a dedicated computer

Event Wiki pages

- **Recommend** that any slides prepared prior to the event be downloaded in pdf format to preserve the clickable links and then uploaded into Wikimedia Commons. That file should then be added to the resources section of the event page. This will allow participants to:
 - Easily access slides
 - Have context about the recommended links
- **Include** other appropriate links on the event page proper. These recommendations came about as a result of feedback received from the Day 2 survey, i.e. "Putting the links in the slides makes them harder to track down and use - it'd be good if all the key stuff was on the event page."

Welcoming new editors

- **Welcome** new editors participating using the [New Zealand welcome template](#) i.e. {{welcome-nz}} ~~~~. SL notes that she had to edit this template as it included information about a past WikiCon and also that it directs editors to User:Schwede66's talk page rather than the talk page of the editor adding the message.
- **Recommend** that the New Zealand welcome template be updated.

Content

- **Recommend** that WANZ and other NZ wiki organisers take note of the following survey responses regarding content they are interested in working on or learning for any future events:
 - More strategies for subtly undermining the irritating people, like adding the 'use NZE' [use New Zealand English] template at the top of every article!
 - Shared biota lists (Critter of the week?)
 - Māori and Pacific history/culture, how to tackle more contested topics
 - New Zealand content, women, underrepresented areas

Venue

- **Recommend** - in anticipation of larger numbers in future New Zealand species edit-a-thons - an alternative venue be considered. Leonard Cockayne Centre was an excellent choice for 15 people. If we had had 25 people, it would have been very tight.

Ticketing

Humanitix is generally an excellent platform for ticketing. It has more functionality than we used in the area of marketing and comms. Humanitix tickets payments were put through the WANZ account with ticketing fees absorbed.

Catering

Angie Stainer of Chef Girl and Bar Boy (chefgirlandbarboy@gmail.com) provided excellent delicious and varied food for both sessions. Quantities were just right. Because of the small size of the fridge at the venue, we opted for delivery just before lunch. Morning tea items were purchased separately.

Organisers ordered 100% vegetarian to simplify dietary requirements. In fact, Angie also provided vegan options. She prefers to communicate by text.

WANZ gear

- **Recommend** that WANZ gear continue to be used. CR collected a well-stocked roll-along suitcase of WANZ gear (multi-boards, extension cables, stationery, first aid kit, etc.) from Dianne Skelton a few days prior to the event. Everything we required was included, including name tag stickers.

- **Recommend** that event organisers check signage during the event. The new WANZ sandwich board was erected outside the venue. This was without incident for the first day but on the second day the wind was so strong it took out one of the inserted panels of the sandwich board. This was easily rectified but is a reminder to organisers to check signage at lunchtime.

Giveaways

- **Recommend** to use WANZ swag. A range of WANZ stickers and WANZ beetle bookmarks were provided in the box of gear. SL also brought along some additional stickers. These were popular with attendees. Some took 2024 tote bags as well.

Finances

The Edit-a-thon 2025 came in well under budget and the unspent portion of the grant (\$2,515) has been returned to WANZ. A link to the Budget and reconciliation is [here](#). The following funds were also deposited into the WANZ account via Humanitix, as we charged \$5 per person per day, and sold a total of 27 tickets:

Ticket sales	\$135.00
Add-on sales	\$0.00
Additional donations	\$0.00
Absorbed fees	\$12.15
Refunds	\$0.00
Total earnings	\$122.85

Future work

The organisers are discussing the possibility of holding another species edit-a-thon in October 2026 to coincide with the New Zealand Plant Conservation Network 2026 Conference to be held at Wharewaka and Ōtari from 12-16 October (either just before or just after the conference, or both). We are also discussing, in addition, running a Wiki workshop provided specifically to conference attendees as part of the conference itself on the “workshop day” which is Monday 12 October.

As previously discussed in this report, as a result of Tim Park’s discussion with the organisers, SL and HM are now interested in participating in the Ōtari Bioblitz to be held in April 2026 during the iNaturalist City Nature Challenge from 24-27 April over ANZAC weekend. The intention is to give a Wiki presence to this Bioblitz, showing us editing Wikipedia in order to educate organisers and participants about Wikipedia.